

DAMAGE EVOLUTION IN AL-SiC COMPOSITES BY X-RAY SYNCHROTRON TOMOGRAPHY AND EXTENDED FINITE ELEMENT MODELING (X-FEM)

Sudhanshu S. Singh¹, Rui Yuan², Jay Oswald², and Nikhilesh Chawla^{1,2}

¹Materials Science and Engineering

²Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering

School for Engineering of Matter, Transport, and Energy (SEMTE)

Arizona State University

Tempe, AZ 85287

United States of America

Email: nchawla@asu.edu, web page: <http://chawla.engineering.asu.edu/wordpress/>

Keywords: Metal-matrix composites (MMCs), SiC particles, X-ray tomography, XFEM

ABSTRACT

Particle-reinforced composites offer high stiffness, high strength, and low density, while maintaining reasonable cost. Their mechanical properties, e.g. tensile strength, depend upon reinforcement characteristics and matrix microstructure. In this study, we have performed *in situ* x-ray synchrotron tomography to understand the damage in 2080 aluminum alloy reinforced with SiC particles in three dimensions. The initial 3D reconstructed microstructure was used as a basis for extended finite element model (XFEM) to simulate damage in the composite when tensile loading is applied.

1 INTRODUCTION

Metal matrix composites (MMCs), especially particle-reinforced metal matrix composites, have a combination of high strength, high stiffness, and low density [1]. The tensile behavior of these MMCs depend upon their microstructure and it has been agreed that damage in particle-reinforced MMCs takes place by a combination of matrix void growth and particle fracture. Most of the studies to understand the damage behavior have been limited to two-dimensional (2D) approaches. These techniques are laborious and restrictive due to the 2D nature of the analysis and therefore 3D techniques are required to understand the damage behavior accurately [2].

Among the many 3D characterization techniques, x-ray tomography is attractive as it is non-destructive and requires minimal sample preparation. It allows for large volumes to be studied, resulting in statistically significant information [3]. X-ray tomography has been successfully applied to characterize the microstructures in 3D for materials such as Al alloys [4, 5], metal matrix composites [6, 7, 8], and Sn-rich alloys [9]. More recently, *in situ* experiments have been conducted to understand the deformation behavior in real-time (4D) such as fatigue [10, 11, 12] and stress corrosion cracking (SCC) [13, 14]. Adequate visualization and fracture quantification is critical to the understanding of damage in MMCs. *In situ* techniques in combination with modeling, such as finite element modeling, are particularly well-suited for examining the initiation and evolution of damage in MMCs.

In order to simulate the complex microstructural geometry of MMCs we adopt the level set method (LSM) and extended finite element method (XFEM) to analyze the fracture of reinforcing particles. The XFEM was developed by Belytschko et al. [15] in order to model crack propagation without the need for remeshing as the crack grows. The central idea of the XFEM is to use enrichment functions that can locally represent discontinuities or other known features of the solution through a partition of

unity [16]. In this approach, the enrichment functions are defined in terms of a signed distance function which implicitly describes the geometry such that material interfaces lie on the zero level set of the distance function. We have published two methods for distance field initialization on adaptively-refined mesh [17]. Some recent examples include work by Yvonnet et al [18] in the study of surface and interface effects in the size-dependent properties of nanocomposites, and work by Zhao et al. [19]. In the latter example, an XFEM algorithm is proposed to predict 3D metamaterial band structures in non-conforming mesh.

2 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

2080 aluminum alloy (3.6% Cu, 1.9% Mg, 0.25% Zr) reinforced with 20 vol.% SiC particles (average particle size of 25 μm) was used in this study. The materials were processed by blending SiC and Al powders, compaction of the powder mixture, hot pressing, and hot extrusion (Alcoa Inc., Alcoa, PA). Details of the powder metallurgy process for fabrication of these composite materials can be found elsewhere [20].

X-ray tomography was performed at the 2-BM beamline of the Advanced Photon Source (APS) at Argonne National Laboratory. The details of the tomography system at 2-BM have been described elsewhere [21, 22]. The Double Multilayer Monochromator installed at beamline 2-BM covers energies between 5 and 30 keV. A LuAG:Ce scintillator screen was coupled with an objective lens and a CoolSnap K4 CCD camera to achieve a specimen pixel size of about 1.466 μm . 2D projections were collected at angular increments of 0.125° over a range of 180° . These 2D projections were then reconstructed using filtered back-projection algorithm.

Figure 1: In situ loading stage to perform tensile testing on MMCs

Electro discharge machining (EDM) was used to obtain dog-bone specimens with a gage length of 2.5 mm and a 0.75 mm square cross-section. Specimens were machined parallel to the extrusion axis. *In-situ* uniaxial tensile tests were carried out on these specimens in the synchrotron using the loading stage shown in Figure 1. The load cell had a 500 N capacity, and the stepper motor had a captive linear actuator capable of 8 μm per step and 12 mm stroke. Actuator was moved to apply load on the sample. Scans were taken at different displacements until failure. The details of the loading stage has been provided elsewhere [10].

3 COMPUTATIONAL PROCEDURE

Due to the enormous quantity of data collected by x-ray tomography and the complexity of the material geometry, a mesh-independent representation of the material microstructure is generated through the fast marching method [23]. Further details of this approach as applied to generating implicit surfaces from x-ray tomography data are described in Yuan et al. [17]. The extended finite element method (XFEM) is then used to solve for the distribution of internal stresses within the composite as it is loaded, where discontinuities in the strain field and eventual discontinuities in the displacement field, i.e. fractures, are represented through enrichment functions [15]. The SiC particles are modeled as isotropic linear elastic materials, with Young's modulus $E = 410$ GPa and Poisson's ratio $\nu = 0.19$. The Al 2080 matrix is modeled as a plastic material with a nonlinear Voce hardening law. The evolution of the yield surface is governed by

$$\sigma_y(\gamma) = \sigma_{y0} + C(1 - e^{-b\gamma}) \quad (1)$$

where the calibrated parameters for Al 2080 alloy were determined to be: $\sigma_{y0} = 370$ MPa, $C = 185$ MPa, and $b = 23.9$.

In our simulations, only rigid body motion is fixed in order to avoid stress concentration on boundary, which can be a potential problem of stability in plastic matrix. Applied traction is increased linearly from zero to the maximum value. At each load step, the increment of traction equals to the quotient of the maximum traction by the total number of load steps. The maximum traction is 430 MPa, which corresponds to the ultimate stress of the specimen tested in experiment.

MMCs exhibit three basic mechanisms for the initiation and growth of damage: cleavage fracture of the brittle particles, decohesion at the interface between matrix and reinforced particles, and ductile failure of the matrix [24]. Failure strengths of brittle materials vary widely from specimen to specimen even though samples are manufactured in the same way and tested under the same condition [25, 26]. Therefore, fracture statistics have to be applied to the failure strengths of brittle materials.

Due to the high brittleness of the particles, once the fracture happens, the crack will immediately expand through the whole particle, leading to the total splitting. While particle and matrix are always perfect bonded, the cracks are assumed to be arrested at the particle-matrix interface. To create a critical fracture plane in particle P_i , an on-plane point p at coordinate \mathbf{x}_f and the plane normal direction \mathbf{n}_f are needed. The cleavage point and the normal direction of fracture surface can be denoted as

$$\mathbf{x}_f = \frac{\int_{\Omega_{P_i}} \mathbf{x} \cdot \sigma_1(\mathbf{x}) d\Omega_{P_i}}{\int_{\Omega_{P_i}} \sigma_1(\mathbf{x}) d\Omega_{P_i}} \quad \mathbf{n}_f = \frac{\int_{\Omega_{P_i}} \mathbf{n}_1 \cdot \sigma_1(\mathbf{x}) d\Omega_{P_i}}{\left\| \int_{\Omega_{P_i}} \mathbf{n}_1 \cdot \sigma_1(\mathbf{x}) d\Omega_{P_i} \right\|} \quad (2)$$

where $\sigma_1(\mathbf{x})$ is the maximum principal stress and \mathbf{n}_1 is the corresponding principal direction. This approximation takes size effect into account since it is always in an integral framework. Weibull fracture probabilities were evaluated for each particle i at each load increment by using the expression [27]

$$P_f^i = 1 - \exp\left(-\frac{1}{V_0^i} \int_{\Omega_{P_i}} \left(\frac{\sigma_m(\mathbf{x})}{\sigma_f}\right)^m d\Omega_{P_i}\right) \quad (3)$$

where V_0^i is the reference volume of particle P_i , σ_f and m are the characteristic strength and Weibull modulus of the SiC particles, respectively.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Figure 2 shows an x-ray tomography slice of extruded SiC reinforced Al 2080 composite after reconstruction. The particles are clearly visible in the image due to phase contrast imaging. A few cracks and pores are visible due to extrusion process.

Figure 2: Reconstructed 2D tomographic slice of SiC particle reinforced Al alloy matrix composite after extrusion.

Figure 3 shows the stress-strain curve for the composite tested at the synchrotron. The experiment was paused at the points indicated in the curve and then a scan was performed to obtain the 3D microstructure at that particular strain value. The composite had a strength of about 438 MPa with a strain-to-failure of about 1.6%.

Figure 3: shows the stress-strain curve for a 2080/SiC/20_p composite tested *in situ*. The data points indicate points where the experiment was paused for tomography.

Figure 4 shows the evolution of damage in the composite with increase in applied stress. It is evident that damage of the composites increase as stress increases, and the damage is dominated by the particle fracture. The onset of damage appears to begin very close to the ultimate strength and the largest increase in particle fracture is between 1% and 1.6% (fracture strain), at the fracture plane.

Figure 4: Evolution of damage in composite with increase in stress. Damage increases with applied stress. At fracture (1.6%) particle fracture is quite predominant.

From figure 2, it is evident that the centers of the SiC particles have the similar gray values to that of the Al alloy matrix, however, the boundary between the Al matrix and SiC particles are clearly distinguishable. Due to the similar gray values of the center of the particles and the matrix, conventional segmentation techniques, such as thresholding, could not be used to separate the SiC particles from the matrix. Instead, a semi-automatic segmentation algorithm known as Livewire was used (Mimics, Materialise, Ann Arbor, MI), which is based on the sharp gradient in gray scale values observed along the boundaries of the SiC particles and Al alloy matrix. The Livewire technique has been explained elsewhere in detail [28]. A selected volume (320 (μm) X 650 (μm) X 104 (μm)) was cropped from the 3D reconstructed volume for the segmentation. The representative 2D slice after segmentation is shown in Figure 5b. The 3D rendering of the SiC particles in 2080 aluminum alloys is shown in figure 6.

Figure 5: (a) Reconstructed 2D tomographic slice of SiC particle reinforced Al alloy matrix composite, (b) Corresponding segmented black and white image showing connecting SiC particles.

Figure 6: 3D volume distribution of SiC particles in 2080 aluminum alloy matrix

The obtained voxel data was imported into our numerical algorithm for distance field initialization. The distance field is initialized by fast marching method, which is very robust and the initialization process can finish in minutes for millions of voxels [17]. Oct-tree mesh is implemented in the consideration of computational effort. Elements close to material interface are sorted and refined.

The following images show particle fracture within plastic matrix. There are 41 particles initialized and 22 particles break at the end. After twice mesh refinements, there are about 113,000 elements. Only rigid body motion is fixed and traction is applied on right surface. Applied traction is increasing linearly from 0 to 430 MPa.

Figure 7: (a) Fracture surfaces in oct-tree mesh wireframe. (b) Axial stress after fracture with fracture surfaces denoted in white.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In situ x-ray synchrotron tomography was used to understand the damage behaviour of SiC particle reinforced 2080 Al alloy matrix composites. XFEM was used to simulate the damage in the composites.

The following important points can be made, as a result of this work:

1. *In-situ* tomography is an excellent technique to understand the damage behaviour of the composites. In the system studied, the damage of the composite was primarily due to the fracture of SiC particles. The damage increased with an increase in stress, with most of the particle fracture taking place very close to the ultimate tensile strength.
2. The XFEM provides a useful and efficient tool for analyzing and interpreting *in-situ* tomography datasets as a nearly exact virtual representation of the geometry can be simulated with minimal pre-processing effort. Such models can be used to better understand how load is transferred to between nearby particles as the material fails.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Use of the Advanced Photon Source was supported by the U.S. Department of Energy, Office of Science, Office of Basic Energy Sciences, under Contract No. DE-AC02-06CH11357.

REFERENCES

- [1] K.K. Chawla and N. Chawla, *Metal Matrix Composites*, Springer Verlag, New York, 2006.
- [2] E. Maire, J. Buffière, L. Salvo, J. Blandin, W. Ludwig and J. Letang, On the application of x-ray microtomography in the field of materials science, *Advanced Engineering Materials*, **3**, 2001, pp. 539-546.
- [3] S. Stock, X-ray microtomography of materials, *International Materials Reviews*, **44**, 1999, pp. 141-164.
- [4] S. S. Singh, C. Schwartzstein, J. J. Williams, X. Xiao, F. D. Carlo and N. Chawla, 3D microstructural characterization and mechanical properties of constituent particles in Al 7075 alloys using X-ray synchrotron tomography and nanoindentation, *Journal of Alloys Compounds*, **602**, 2014, pp. 163-174.
- [5] J. Kastner, B. Harrer and H.P. Degischer, High resolution cone beam X-ray computed tomography of 3D-microstructures of cast Al-alloys, *Materials Characterization*, **62**, 2011, pp. 99-107.
- [6] J. Williams, Z. Flom, A. Amell, N. Chawla, X. Xiao and F. De Carlo, Damage evolution in SiC particle reinforced Al alloy matrix composites by X-ray synchrotron tomography, *Acta Materialia*, **58**, 2010, pp. 6194-6205.
- [7] P. Hruby, S. S. Singh, J. J. Williams, X. Xiao, F. De Carlo and N. Chawla, Fatigue crack growth in SiC particle reinforced Al alloy matrix composites at high and low R-ratios by *in situ* X-ray synchrotron tomography, *International Journal of Fatigue*, **68**, 2014, pp. 136-143.
- [8] L. Babout, E. Maire, J. Buffière and R. Fougères, Characterization by X-ray computed tomography of decohesion, porosity growth and coalescence in model metal matrix composites, *Acta Materialia*, **49**, 2001, pp. 2055-2063.
- [9] E. Padilla, V. Jakkali, L. Jiang and N. Chawla, Quantifying the effect of porosity on the evolution of deformation and damage in Sn-based solder joints by X-ray microtomography and microstructure-based finite element modeling, *Acta Materialia*. **60**, 2012, pp. 4017-4026.
- [10] S. S. Singh, J. J. Williams, P. Hruby, X. Xiao, F. De Carlo and N. Chawla, *In situ* experimental techniques to study the mechanical behavior of materials using X-ray synchrotron tomography, *Integrating Materials and Manufacturing Innovation*, **3**, 2014, pp. 9.

- [11] P.J. Withers and M. Preuss, Fatigue and damage in structural materials studied by X-ray tomography, *Annual Review of Materials Research*, **42**, 2012, pp. 81-103.
- [12] S.S. Singh, J.J. Williams, X. Xiao, F. De Carlo and N. Chawla, *In situ* three dimensional (3D) x-ray synchrotron tomography of corrosion fatigue in Al7075 alloy, *Fatigue of Materials II: Advances and Emergences in Understanding, Materials Science and Technology* (Eds. T.S. Srivatsan, M. Ashraf Imam, R. Srinivasan), Pittsburgh, A John Wiley & Sons Inc. 2012, pp. 17-25.
- [13] S. S. Singh, J. J. Williams, M. F. Lin, X. Xiao, F. De Carlo and N. Chawla, *In situ* investigation of high humidity stress corrosion cracking of 7075 aluminum alloy by three-dimensional (3d) x-ray synchrotron tomography, *Materials Research Letters*, **4**, 2014, pp. 217-220.
- [14] L. Babout, T. J. Marrow, D. Engelberg and P. J. Withers, X-ray microtomographic observation of intergranular stress corrosion cracking in sensitised austenitic stainless steel. *Materials Science and Technology*, **22**, 2006, pp. 1068-1075.
- [15] T. Belytschko and Tom Black, Elastic crack growth in finite elements with minimal remeshing, *International Journal for Numerical Methods in Engineering*, **45**, 1999, pp. 601-620.
- [16] I. Babuska and J. M. Melenk, The partition of unity finite element method, *Maryland Univ College Park Inst for Physical Science and Technology*, 1995.
- [17] R. Yuan, S. S. Singh, N. Chawla and J. Oswald, Efficient methods for implicit geometrical representation of complex material microstructures, *International Journal for Numerical Methods in Engineering*, **98**, 2014, pp. 79-91.
- [18] J. Yvonnet, H. Le Quang and Q-C. He, An XFEM/level set approach to modelling surface/interface effects and to computing the size-dependent effective properties of nanocomposites, *Computational Mechanics*, **42**, 2008, pp. 119-131.
- [19] J. Zhao, Y. Li and W. K. Liu, Predicting band structure of 3D mechanical metamaterials with complex geometry via XFEM, *Computational Mechanics*, **55**, 2015, pp. 659-672.
- [20] N. Chawla, C. Andres, J. W. Jones and J. E. Allison, Effect of SiC volume fraction and particle size on the fatigue resistance of a 2080 Al/SiC composite, *Metallurgical and Materials Transactions A*, **29**, 1998, 2843-2854.
- [21] F. De Carlo and B. Tieman, High-throughput x-ray microtomography system at the Advanced Photon Source beamline 2-BM, *SPIE*, **5535**, 2004, pp. 644-651.
- [22] F. De Carlo, P. Albee, Y.S. Chu, D.C. Mancini, B. Tieman and S.Y. Wang, High-throughput real-time x-ray microtomography at the Advanced Photon Source, *SPIE*, **4503**, 2002, pp. 1-13.
- [23] J. A. Sethian, A fast marching level set method for monotonically advancing fronts, *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, **93**, 1996, pp. 1591-1595.
- [24] A. Eckschlager, W. Han and H. J. Bohm, A unit cell model for brittle fracture of particles embedded in a ductile matrix, *Computational Materials Science*, **25**, 2002, 85-91.
- [25] C. Lu, R. Danzer and F. D. Fischer, Fracture statistics of brittle materials: Weibull or normal distribution, *Physical Review E*, **65**, 2002, 067102.

[26] R. Doremus, Fracture statistics: A comparison of the normal, Weibull, and type I extreme value distributions, *Journal of Applied Physics*, **54**, 1983, 193-198.

[27] W. Weibull, A statistical distribution function of wide applicability, *Journal of Applied Mechanics*, **18**, 1951, pp. 293-297.

[28] W. A. Barrett and E. N. Mortensen, Interactive live-wire boundary extraction, *Medical Image Analysis*, **1**, 1996, 331-341.